

MEDIATIZED EU – Mediatized Discourses on Europeanization and their Representation in Public Perceptions

D3.2	Policy Recommendations for Local Policymakers
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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Ireland	5
2.1. Abstract	5
2.2. Executive Summary	5
2.3. Policy Recommendations	6
2.4. Final Remarks	9
3. Georgia	10
3.1. Introduction.....	10
3.2. Media analysis	10
3.3. Interviews with political and media actors	12
3.4. Population Survey	14
3.5. Policy Recommendations	15
4. Spain.....	19
4.1. Abstract	19
4.2. Executive Summary	19
4.3. Policy Recommendations	20
4.4. Final Remarks	24
5. Estonia.....	26
5.1. Abstract	26
5.2. Executive Summary	26
5.3. Policy Recommendations	27
5.4. Final Remarks	28
6. Portugal	30
6.1. Abstract.....	30
6.2. Executive Summary	30
6.3. Policy Recommendations	31
6.4. Final Remarks	33
7. Belgium.....	35
7.1. Abstract	35
7.2. Executive Summary	35

7.3.	Policy Recommendations	36
7.4.	Final Remarks	38
8.	<i>Hungary</i>	39
8.1.	Abstract.....	39
8.2.	Executive Summary.....	39
8.3.	Policy Recommendations	40
8.4.	Final Remarks	43

Policy Recommendations for Local Policymakers

1. Introduction

1.1. About the MEDIATIZED EU Project

The aim of the MEDIATIZED EU project is to study the framing of the European integration project and Europeanization in traditional and new media outlets, and to study the EU's representations in public opinion. The project is based on the premise the media's framing of politics can have a profound impact on modern politics through reshaping "the fabric of politics" (Axford, 2001, 3). Scholars argue that news coverage is becoming increasingly negative or cynical. This is paralleled by an increased alienation of the public from both political processes and the media (Moog & Sluyter-Beltrao, 2001). Some scholars have named this phenomenon the "spiral of cynicism". This spiral of cynicism manifests itself as a "spiral of Euroscepticism" when EU related politics are discussed (Galpin & Trenz, 2016, 2). Media negativity in the EU coverage, whether attributed to the media itself or originating from Eurosceptic parties and subsequently disseminated by media, undermines the democratic legitimacy of the EU and leads to civic distrust (Ibid., 4). According Galpin and Trenz (2016), media frames that are shaped by negativity bias, especially when amplified on social media, could explain the salience of Eurosceptic opinions in the public sphere, prompting political parties to contest EU policies using predominantly negative terms. As a result, the "permissive consensus" that existed on the EU has been replaced by "constraining dissensus" (Hooghe & Marks, 2008).

Bearing all that in mind, MEDIATIZED EU attempted to study the role of the media in fostering or alternatively hampering the EU integration project. To achieve this goal, the research teams in the seven target countries conducted an analysis of media discourses on the EU during the period of nine months (July 2021 to March 2022), conducted interviews with representatives of media and political elites (50 interviews per country), as well as a general population survey (1000 participants per country). This tripartite research design helped as to achieve the following objectives:

1. To study how the traditional and new online media frame the European integration project and Europeanization while paying attention to the pragmatic and identity-based factors utilized by the media in discussing the EU.
2. To explore the role of political and media elites in the media framing of the European integration project.
3. To trace the interconnections between the political and media elites' discourses, EU framing and public opinion.

More about the project: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101004534>

1.2. Executive Summary and purpose of the deliverable

The document corresponds to Deliverable 3.2 – Policy Recommendations for Local Policymakers:

“A policy recommendation package for the local policymakers in each target country, developed by all partners, and led by TalTech and UANE”.

Based on the research findings involving media analysis, interviews with political and media elites, and public opinion surveys in the seven target countries, the research team in each target country designed a policy recommendation report for national policymakers. While each target country has its own political particularities, some issues of concern were common to almost all target countries. This includes the need for measures to counter political polarization, the need to increase the knowledge level about the EU and the need to engage the public more, and the need to tackle disinformation.

The aim of the national policy recommendations report is to enable local policymakers to develop effective strategies to counter mediatized representations that could hamper the European integration project due to negativity bias or because they contain disinformation or misinformation. Additionally, the policy recommendations can assist national policymakers in planning awareness-raising campaigns for citizens, adapted to local political contexts.

1.3. List of Partner Beneficiaries Involved

EU Partners:

Dublin City University (DCU), Ireland
Universitas Nebrissensis SA (UANE), Spain
Tallinna Tehnikaulikool (TalTech), Estonia
Centro de Estudos Sociais (CES), Portugal
European Neighbourhood Council (ENC), Belgium
Budapesti Corvinus Egyetem (CUB), Hungary

Non-EU Partners:

Center for Social Sciences (CSS), Georgia

2. Ireland

2.1. Abstract

Ireland's political and media elites, as well as an overwhelming proportion of the public, display a predominantly positive attitude towards the EU and the country's ongoing Europeanisation. The discursive sphere is dominated by the pragmatic "mutual benefit" framing, underscoring Ireland's special relationship with the EU built on the shared European values of human rights, democracy and rule of law, viewed by the Irish elites and public as intrinsic to Irish identity. At the same time, this positive sentiment is concurrent with a low level of public knowledge about EU affairs and the internal workings of EU membership, and this disconnect creates a gap that could be exploited by actors seeking to polarize Irish society in the service of anti-EU agendas or identitarian politics. The Irish case, characterized by dominant pragmatic pro-EU attitudes and a robust independent media sphere, coupled with a lack of public "EU literacy", offers timely insights for exploring the potential threats to EU solidarity posed by disinformation, disenfranchisement and political polarization, and the potential policy interventions aimed at preventing these destructive tendencies and building on the shared European values and common pragmatic benefits in order to develop a more robust member state integration and more enthusiastic public participation in the European project.

2.2. Executive Summary

Across the public sphere, media and elite circles, Ireland displays a predominantly supportive attitude towards its relationship with and membership in the EU. In the media and elite discourses, this pro-EU positivity owes much to the "mutual benefit" framing, underscoring Ireland's special history with the Union and its own influence as an actor in the EU, despite being a small state. Another shared elite discourse highlights the solidarity grounded in shared core EU values of human rights, democracy and the rule of law. The Irish elites' positive view of the EU has been further bolstered by the Union's stance in the Brexit negotiations, where it has been sensitive to both the economic concerns shared by its members and Ireland's unique concerns regarding the peace process in Northern Ireland and the border issue.

While critical views of the EU exist among the political and media elites, the debate mostly hinges on pragmatic considerations, and focuses on specific policies, benefits or costs of EU membership. Examples of critical reflections on EU's role include, for instance, its involvement in Ireland's policies as a technological innovation and business hub; Ireland's spotty track record on delivering on climate change reforms; or the more recent debate about the EU's common defence and security policy brought on by Russia's invasion of Ukraine. However, any anti-EU counter-discourses have thus far

remained on the fringes and garnered little media coverage, however much these far-right (and occasionally far-left) voices attempt to manipulate the discursive space through capitalising on key concerns such as the fall out of Russia's invasion of Ukraine and its impact on Irish military neutrality; the concerns about migration, housing and cost of living; or perceived threats to national autonomy and Irish identity allegedly posed by the EU.

The public in Ireland has consistently shown strong support for EU integration and Europeanisation, and this is confirmed by the results of our population survey, which found that Irish citizens display positive and mostly pragmatic support for EU membership. However, these high levels of positive attitudes towards the EU are coexistent with a lack of awareness about the key structures and mechanisms of EU governance, decision-making and operations. Our research finds that media coverage of Ireland's Europeanisation is dominated by elite actors (politicians, policymakers, journalists), and while the media seek to domesticate EU affairs by reporting on them in light of national or local agendas, there is a resulting disconnect between the public needs for information and explanatory reporting, and the elites' taking public support for EU integration for granted. This low level of "EU literacy" is of particular importance as it puts into question the stability and longevity of public support for the EU where there is a lack of citizen engagement on core issues. Today, the Irish public is also becoming more concerned about the threats of disinformation, particularly circulating in social media. Recent elite and media interviews also show concern for the rising influence of far-right actors in European politics who seek to exploit key (legitimate) economic and social concerns in the service of polarizing the Irish society through manipulative identitarian framing and to push the public sentiment towards a more divisive and Eurosceptic agenda and away from the shared EU values and interests.

Based on our findings, the Irish case is characterized by dominant pragmatic pro-EU discourses among the elites and the public, with a healthy dose of critical takes, taking place a robust independent media sphere. These conditions, however, are coupled with a lack of public knowledge about EU and how it functions, which creates potential gaps that could be exploited by anti-EU forces seeking to play the identity card and undermine European unity and solidarity. The Irish data offers insights for policy interventions to address the potential threats to EU solidarity posed by disinformation, disenfranchisement and political polarization, to prevent these destructive tendencies, and to build on the shared values and common benefits towards a more robust European integration strategy and inspiring more enthusiastic public participation in the European project.

2.3. Policy Recommendations

1. **Diversify the spectrum of voices present in debates on Europeanisation and support in-depth media coverage of EU affairs.** While trust in media in Ireland

remains high overall, in-depth independent reporting and explanatory journalism require more stable and consistent material supports. Irish media outlets covering EU issues should achieve greater specialisation to shed light on a range of EU-related issues and deepen quality long-form reporting covering key debates on policies and values. Media should also prioritise platforming a range of voices outside of the conventional elite circles, reaching out to academic experts, industry specialists, non-government organisations, and civil society and community, as well as citizens themselves, to foster a broader, more participatory debate about the EU and Ireland's relationship with it. This should include fostering specialisation on EU topics among journalists and media representatives to allow for deeper coverage and investigative reporting. A specific role in this mission lies with Irish public service media, which should be further supported in their efforts to reform and improve the delivery of public service broadcasting and online content. Ongoing regulatory reform currently underway (i.e., the creation of Coimisiún na Meán, Ireland's new broadcast and online media regulator also in charge of media development) should continue to further buttress supports for public service media and ensure greater pluralism and diversity in the media sphere, which should positively impact the diversity and availability of coverage of EU affairs.

2. **Further enhance citizen media literacy and digital literacy.** The Irish public are increasingly concerned about disinformation or misinformation online, as well as the rise of populist and divisive rhetoric around issues such as migration or climate change. At the same time, Irish internet users are concerned about potential restrictions and censorship of political debates on online platforms. Such a situation requires a more focused, participatory approach to enhance citizen media literacy, especially amid growing reliance on digital media for news and information. Building on the work of cross-sectoral initiatives such as Media Literacy Ireland and bringing multi-stakeholder fora together to devise sustainable literacy support and development strategies based on best practices from across the EU and the globe should be central to ensuring a more informed public armed with the best tools and skills to make informed decisions about analysing news and information, online and offline.
3. **Strengthen societal resilience to online disinformation.** Amid broader European concerns about media manipulation, disinformation and media literacy, there has been an ongoing debate in Ireland about the quality of news media and regulation of online political advertising, leading to an overall decline of trust in news. The use of disinformation in political disputes and campaigns, resulting in growing political polarisation and mistrust in public institutions, should be the focus of attention in Ireland's efforts to tackle these issues. Despite the emerging mechanisms and institutional frameworks in place, such as the Online Safety and Media Regulation Act 2022 and the creation of Coimisiún na Meán, and Ireland's active participation in European initiatives such as the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation and the East StratCom

TaskForce, a more forward-thinking strategy to counter disinformation should be developed. Such a strategy should necessarily include the independent media sector, and the digital platform industry to ensure accountability and best practice adoption but should also actively involve non-governmental organisations and community groups, to understand the needs of key civic groups, adapt literacy and disinformation initiatives to these needs, and address emergent concerns as they arise.

4. **Foster increased citizen knowledge of political and EU-related issues.** Despite media efforts to domesticate coverage of EU affairs in Ireland, citizens, especially those with lower incomes and education levels, remain detached from an in-depth understanding of how EU policy impacts their everyday lives on a practical level, beyond simplistic framings of economic benefits. The relatively low turnout in the recent European elections in Ireland also serves as evidence of this gap. The scope of the mediated debate about Ireland-EU relations and European integration should encompass a broad spectrum of issues related to EU economic and political life, but also about social and cultural aspects, educational opportunities, the environment, and other topics of relevance, geared towards the wider public. Media coverage featuring a variety of diverse voices should be complemented by enhanced participation of Irish actors and stakeholders in EU cultural, social and scientific life, deepening citizen awareness of the European public sphere and the EU's global influence.
5. **Support greater citizen engagement with EU institutions through new opportunities for participation.** Fostering more active interest and engagement in EU-related affairs and debates among citizens emerges as one of the most pressing issues for media and political elites. Media coverage should also focus on public interest aspects and explanatory reporting about opportunities for citizen participation in EU affairs in practical ways. Such efforts should support grassroots, civil society and community contributions to normative and political initiatives, as well as provide opportunities for training and skills exchange to promote community leadership initiatives and cross-EU collaborations.
6. **Design and implement a more robust strategy for protecting citizen agency and rights online.** Aside from concerns about disinformation in digital spaces and declining trust in news media, the Irish public is also worried about the security of personal data on the Internet and its use for targeting the political ads people see, undermining free and fair competition between political parties. Irish institutions (e.g., Coimisiún na Meán, the Data Protection Commission, or the National Cyber Security Centre) responsible for implementing relevant European directives, such as the EU Audiovisual Media Services Directive, the Digital Services Act or the EU Network and Information Security Directive, and operationalising national regulatory acts and strategy documents such as the Online Safety and Media Regulation Act 2022 or the National Cyber Security

Strategy, should prioritise the protection of fundamental rights online and seek to enhance civic agency and individual security, giving citizens greater control over their data, news flows and discursive spaces online. These institutional actors should also continue to hold digital platforms and business and political actors accountable for abusing online freedoms and algorithmic/data mining tools and ensure ordinary citizens enjoy robust protections and redress mechanisms in this respect. These measures are especially crucial given Ireland's leading role in the European digital market as the host of many large online platforms' European headquarters.

2.4. Final Remarks

These policy recommendations summarise the initial findings of the Irish research in the context of the MEDIATIZED EU project. They specifically focus on the low levels of awareness of EU affairs among the Irish public, the threats of political polarisation to citizens and media, the circulation of disinformation with the aim of undermining the European integration project, whether by foreign governments or domestic political groups, and the decline of trust in media. We contextualise these key findings through the discursive framing in elite and public opinions and identify key policy measures needed to enhance citizen knowledge and engagement, bolster trust in independent media, promote media literacy, tackle disinformation, and safeguard a pluralistic and transparent media and political landscape in Ireland.

Measures to combat threats of interference and manipulation during pan-European crises, negative consequences for national security or fundamental rights, threats to the independent media landscape or lack of media literacy and "EU literacy" among citizens are highlighted, in order to facilitate the adoption of effective strategies to respond to manipulative, identity-driven Eurosceptic discourses and counter disinformation, while ensuring an informed, empowered citizenry keen on political participation and showcasing greater awareness of and interest in the European project and its values and benefits for the Irish public. These recommendations ultimately aim to contribute to a more robust strategy for EU integration and more enthusiastic public participation in the European project.

3. Georgia

3.1. Introduction

The proposed policy paper is developed within the framework of the MEDIATIZED EU project, which aims to study how media narratives are shaped to either advance or hinder the European project and how these narratives resonate with the public, by focusing on the interplay among elites, media, and the public. The project provides a comparative cross-country analysis involving seven target countries: Georgia, Ireland, Belgium, Portugal, Hungary, Estonia and Spain. Considering the elite-media-public triangle as the primary research focus for this project, the research stages involved media analysis examining pro-European and anti-European discourses represented across various media outlets; in-depth interviews with governmental and oppositional political actors, as well as media representatives, identifying the patterns and specifics of these discourses; and a representative survey of the population studying the patterns of media consumption and the attitudes toward the EU. In the subsequent sections, major findings from the three stages of research conducted in Georgia are discussed, and a set of recommendations addressing various stakeholders is proposed.

3.2. Media analysis

Main actors and dominant discourses.

The media analysis is based on an examination of six popular media outlets in Georgia in the period of July 2021-March 2022, though we also added an important period of June 2022 – when Georgia was refused candidate status – to the media analysis. Recent surveys indicate that television and the internet are the primary sources of information for Georgia’s population. In the recent past, almost all Georgian printed media have transitioned to the online format. With the project aiming to uncover media discourses influencing or hindering the European project, the focus included media outlets with both pro-European and anti-European rhetoric (print/online media). As for television, considering that none of the TV outlets self-positioned as anti-European, we targeted public vis-a-vis the most popular/trusted private TV channels (pro-governmental and pro-oppositional). Both quantitative and qualitative content analyses have been utilized to scrutinize the data gathered from the aforementioned media outlets, followed by a thorough critical discourse analysis.

Quantitative content analysis revealed a top-five group of actors voicing the discourses on Georgia’s European integration in the selected media outlets, composed of journalists, the ruling party (Georgian Dream), pro-European opposition, the EU, and NGOs. Eight board discursive units have been identified through the quantitative and qualitative content analysis of the target media: 1. The government’s/opposition’s role in Georgia’s European integration; 2. Russia’s role in Georgia’s European integration; 3.

The EU's support of human rights (a pragmatic factor); 4. The EU's financial support (a pragmatic factor); 5. Georgia's aspiration towards European integration (a pragmatic factor); 6. "I am Georgian and, therefore, I am European" (an identity factor); 7. How European is Georgia? (Both pragmatic & identity considerations are implied); 8. The EU's interference in Georgia's internal affairs (a sovereignty consideration).

Representing the EU and the country's Europeanization.

The analysis has substantiated that the media landscape intricately mirrors the highly polarized political terrain in Georgia. Pro-governmental, pro-oppositional, pro-European, and anti-European media outlets contribute to the creation of divergent discourses regarding Georgia's European integration and Europeanization, thereby constructing distinct versions of reality. These constructions employ various discursive strategies and ideological schemas. They operate as discursive manipulations, strategically designed to persuade the audience. The tactics employed include the dichotomy of Us vs. Them, the politics of fear, topoi, intertextuality, fabrications, code switching, local coherence, modalities, metaphors, and allegories. This nuanced examination highlights the multifaceted ways in which media outlets shape and influence public perceptions through strategic discourse construction. In all media outlets, the prevailing discourses focus on the blame game regarding the ruling party's or the opposition's deviation from the European trajectory, accompanied by accusations of pro-Russianness. As anticipated, pro-governmental media emphasizes the opposition's deviation, while pro-oppositional and other outlets highlight the government's deviation from the European path. The latter, prevalent in all media outlets, is even voiced in the pro-governmental one. While these discourses spark discussions on certain pragmatic (EU's human rights support, financial aid, membership prospects) and identity (reactivation of Georgians' European identity, "mental Europeanization") considerations, the prevalence of the blame game - stemming from both governmental and opposition parties - leaves a very limited space for discussing and scrutinizing substantial issues related to the process of Europeanization.

Furthermore, the analysis of additional periods (June 2022; March/May 2023) revealed three major lines of findings: 1. Starting already from 2021, Georgian Government engages in a discursive opposition with the EU representatives. While in the beginning of the research period, this opposition was of a defensive nature, after Russia's invasion of Ukraine, the discursive disengagement escalated and shifted to an offensive opposition articulated, for instance, in blaming the EU actors for pursuing double standards and dragging Georgia into the war; 2. Illiberal discourses, which strongly relied on nationalist (with the focus on protecting sovereignty from the west) and homophobic (with the focus on Georgian traditional values being threatened by liberal values) ideas used to be marginal, voiced exclusively by the pro-Russian media outlet GeWorld until the start of the war in Ukraine. However, in the aftermath of the war, and particularly in the milieu of increased tension between the ruling party and EU actors, illiberal discourses became mainstream, i.e. being voiced by the high-level

governmental officials and penetrating the mainstream pro-governmental TV channel “Imedi”; 3. The blame games between governmental and oppositional actors built around the accusations of deviating from the European course is a major subject shaping the extreme polarization of both political and media spheres in the country. Through the usage of specific discursive strategies (e.g. fabrications, topoi, the politics of fear, ideological schema) actors on both poles of the contestation have been instrumentalizing the issue of Europeanization for discrediting their opponents, thereby reinforcing the current polarization.

3.3. Interviews with political and media actors

This part of the research delves into the analysis of interviews utilizing Q methodology with political and media elites in Georgia, conducted from October 2022 to January 2023. A total of 50 participants – 24 politicians (representing the ruling party and parliamentary opposition parties) and 26 media representatives (journalists, editors, producers) focusing on Georgia’s foreign policy matters – participated in in-depth interviews. The respondents were provided with 25 widely circulated statements on Georgia’s Europeanization derived from the previous stage of the research, i.e. analysis of the six popular media outlets. They were then prompted to position these statements on the provided Q grid, assessing their importance and expressing personal agreement/disagreement. Following the grid completion, the respondents were asked to elaborate on their choices and to discuss their rationale for rating the statements in a particular way. The data underwent quantitative analysis through correlation and factor analyses for Q methodology (in the Ken-Q-Analysis online software) as well as qualitative content analysis and critical discourse analysis for the subsequent in-depth interviews.

Factor analysis - Strong political and media polarization.

The quantitative Q analysis identified three significant factors reflecting diverse perspectives on Georgia's European integration and Europeanization. Factor 1 consists of oppositional political and media actors, Factor 2 consists of governmental political and media actors, and Factor 3 includes a single respondent – a representative of a pro-Russian media outlet. Thus, these factors can be titled as “Oppositional Actors” (Factor 1), “Governmental Actors” (Factor 2), and “Pro-Russian Actor” (Factor 3). The primary theme that unites the opposition parties and pro-oppositional media outlets in Factor 1 revolves around the concerns regarding Georgia's present foreign policy issues: it centers on the deviation discourse and hence, the ruling party’s role in leading the departure from the European course. The primary distinction between Factor 1 and Factor 2 lies in their perspectives on the ruling party’s role in the country’s European integration: as anticipated, governmental actors reject the idea of their deviation from Georgia's European path.

It should be mentioned that in contrast to the consistent governmental rhetoric observed in the media analysis, asserting the opposition's deviation from the European path, the interviews with the ruling party politicians and pro-governmental media actors revealed a notable divergence: unlike their earlier claims, they stressed that neither they nor their political rivals deviated from the European course. This highlights the manipulative nature of governmental discourses, specifically, their use of the deviation discourse to discredit opposition parties in the eyes of wider society. Factor 3 turned out to be quite loaded with discursive manipulations. It is very typical for pro-Russian actors to claim support for Georgia's political neutrality, asserting their objection to the external forces determining the country's fate. Yet, on closer examination, the term "external power" refers specifically to "the West" rather than Russia. Consequently, they avoid acknowledging that distancing from the Western influence implies falling under the Russian influence for Georgia.

Elite perceptions of the EU and the country's Europeanization.

Three core themes were derived from the interviews with politicians and media representatives: Georgia's political orientation, pragmatic considerations linked to the country's European integration, and identity considerations stemming from the country's Europeanization. Summarizing key points on Georgia's political orientation, the views of political and media elites converge on four interrelated meta-arguments. The Choice argument explores Georgia's options, framing it within the dichotomy of the West vs. Russia, often viewed in terms of development vs. backsliding and liberalism vs. authoritarianism. The Small State argument highlights the country's vulnerability due to its size, resource constraints, and security challenges, especially in the face of Russian threats. The Geopolitics argument delves into the clash between Russia and the EU/West, emphasizing Russia's strategic interest in countering Western influences, leading to its attempts to divert countries like Georgia from the European path. Lastly, the Influence Mechanisms argument examines the tools employed by Russia and the EU, emphasizing soft power strategies such as Russian propaganda and EU conditionality that point to the power imbalance between these actors and Georgia.

Pragmatic considerations of political and media actors focus on two prevailing discourses: One emphasizing the EU's role in safeguarding Georgia's territorial unity and the other highlighting the EU's role in supporting human rights in the country. Identity considerations related to Georgia's European integration center on the alignment of EU-associated liberal values with the Georgian identity. Political and media representatives generate overlapping discourses, drawing on historical and cultural arguments to naturalize Georgia's European integration. The polarization between the government and opposition surfaces in accusations of betraying European liberal values, with the opposition critiquing the ruling party's conservative discourse as deviating from the European path, while the ruling party questioning the authenticity of the opposition's liberalism. This demonstrates the instrumentalization of Europeanization by both governmental and oppositional actors as a discursive strategy

to legitimize own actions and discredit the opponent, which points to the strategic usage of Europeanization, amplifying the country's political polarization.

3.4. Population Survey

The survey (conducted during July-August 2023) aimed to explore public perceptions of the EU and Europeanization from a representative sample of citizens aged 18 and above (excluding occupied territories), utilizing a multistage stratified clustered sampling design. 1022 interviews were successfully conducted. Among the survey participants, 46% identified as male and 54% as female. The age distribution reveals a significant presence of the 45-64 age group (36%), highlighting the prevalence of middle-aged individuals. Education levels indicate that more than half of the survey participants completed secondary education, while the third holds a higher degree. Employment-wise, 40% are currently engaged in paid work. Settlement types are distributed as follows: 43% of the respondents live in villages, 28% in the capital, and 27% in other urban areas.

Media Consumption and Political polarization.

The data revealed that from the list of media outlets the pro-governmental "Imedi" TV is the most popular one, while the party-neutral online newspaper Netgazeti is the least popular one. This indicates that the majority of the population relies on the news from the media outlets hostile to each other, contributing to the deepening of media and political polarization. However, it should be noted that the local media was most often associated with disseminating disinformation. Correlation analysis showed that the viewers of pro-governmental media perceive oppositional actors as major disseminators of disinformation and vice versa, highlighting the link between media consumption patterns and political polarization. Approximately half of the participants perceive media coverage as polarized, and the elites are viewed as divided over EU-related matters. Overall, more than 70% of survey respondents consider both the media and political environment to be polarized and believe that the Georgian political elites should be more unified.

Public Knowledge and Attitudes toward the EU.

Examining public attitudes and perceptions of the EU is crucial for understanding how the media and political elites' use of Europeanization influences the views of the Georgian population. In terms of awareness regarding EU-related issues, the data point to a widespread lack of public knowledge. Media consumption plays a pivotal role, with pro-governmental media linked to lower EU-related knowledge, conservative views, perception of the EU as a threat to national sovereignty, satisfaction with the ways the

government deals with EU-related issues, and a positive stance toward Russia. In contrast, pro-oppositional media consumption correlates positively with EU knowledge and the acknowledgment of pragmatic gains stemming from the EU.

Regarding general attitudes toward the EU, positive attitudes prevail over the skeptical ones. However, a considerable number of participants lack a definitive stance on the benefits associated with Georgia's European integration. Despite the significant level of uncertainty among the Georgian public, around 60% tend to agree that the EU plays a vital role in safeguarding human rights and democracy in Georgia and contributes to Georgia's economic progress.

The influence of the EU on Georgian identity and values is a subject frequently exploited by anti-Western and pro-Russian propaganda. One-third of the respondents express uncertainty about whether the EU jeopardizes Georgia's national identity and traditional values, or encroaches on Georgia's internal affairs and sovereignty. Public perceptions concerning the EU's perceived double standards toward Georgia elicit the greatest uncertainty among respondents, with half of them unable to give a definitive answer. Among those survey participants who do respond, 30.3% believe that the EU operates with double standards toward Georgia, compared to those holding the opposing view (18.7%).

To sum up, although the data indicate that the Georgian public generally has a positive view of the EU, considerable levels of uncertainty and limited awareness of EU-related information are evident. This suggests that the pervasiveness of the blame games among political actors and the lack of substantial discussions regarding EU-related issues amplified with the mediatized manipulation and instrumentalization of Europeanization discourses contribute to the ambiguity of the public opinion. Predictably, this renders the Georgian population more susceptible to anti-European/anti-Western propaganda and disinformation, especially through pro-governmental media outlets.

Given the above findings, policy recommendations have been developed revolving around two broad dimensions, which have been crystallized regarding the mediatized discourses on Europeanization and their resonance among the public in Georgia: (1) Depolarization of the discourses on Europeanization and (2) Fighting disinformation related to it. Recommendations target specific actors who have the agency of creating and/or reproducing these discourses.

3.5. Policy Recommendations

Coordinated efforts among political actors, media, and civil society are crucial to ensure that the representation of the EU and Georgia's Europeanization in public discourses is consistent with the country's foreign policy objectives. However, it should be underlined that the Georgian political landscape has undergone significant changes

with the adoption (May 28, 2024) of the so-called “foreign agents” law, primarily targeting civil society and independent media. Indeed, the primary recommendation to the government of Georgia, led by the Georgian Dream Party, would be to repeal this law, cease undermining Georgia’s European integration, and normalize political relations with Georgia’s European/Western partners. The following set of recommendations will only be feasible and realistic within the framework of democratic governance and the rule of law. To this end, it is fundamental to:

Build consensus on critical national issues such as European integration, economic development, and national security; ensure transparency in policy making and accountability of government actions to build public trust; uphold democratic principles and rule of law to demonstrate commitment to good governance practices; provide support to civil society organizations that promote transparency, accountability, and civic engagement, and empower these organizations to monitor political processes and hold leaders accountable;

Strengthen diplomatic relations with the European Union and other international partners to reinforce Georgia's commitment to European integration. This includes honoring international agreements and engaging constructively in bilateral and multilateral forums.

Depolarization of the discourses on Europeanization.

Georgian government and MPs representing both Georgian Dream and opposition parties should strive to:

Develop responsible and constructive political discourse that focuses on policy solutions rather than personal attacks or divisive rhetoric.

Promote media pluralism and independence through ensuring the independence of media outlets from political influence.

Emphasize benefits of European integration, such as economic growth, security cooperation, and cultural exchange, through positive and inclusive narratives in media and public discourse. Furthermore, highlighting shared values and mutual benefits can counteract divisive rhetoric.

The following recommendations highlight the gaps that need to be filled up with regards to the work of journalists and other media actors:

Ensure a better training and capacity building for journalists in scrutinizing the political actors’ blame games, so that they are able to put those actors back on track with the issues that are substantial, instead of allowing a superficial instrumentalization of the issues related to the EU and the country’s Europeanization.

As a result, to dedicate more airtime/space to the substantial discussions of the subject matter in the primetime programs (main news program of the day and evening talk-shows).

In order to ensure the implementation of the abovementioned recommendations, it is also essential to provide journalists with a better education (both formal and informal) about the matters of the EU, its institutions, internal and external procedures and the Europeanization process in general.

Civil society organizations can play an important role in achieving the goal of depolarization of Europeanization discourses by:

Facilitating constructive discussions about the ways and mechanisms of depolarizing discourses on Europeanization, involving different groups such as academia, experts, media and journalists themselves. These discussions should ideally involve polarized political actors too. Constructive discussions within, between and among these groups could create the space for exchange, which in turn can serve as a ground for further regeneration of healthier communication.

In cooperation with researchers, constant monitoring of the discourses and narratives of the political and media actors regarding the EU and Europeanization. Using the results of this monitoring for giving feedback and recommendations to the actors responsible for creating these discourses.

Fighting disinformation.

The major recommendation towards the government of Georgia is still to develop a complex state vision on the hybrid threats and have a clear political strategy against disinformation. Georgia's Department of Strategic Communications, or StratComs, was established in 2015 as part of a significant UK-led NATO initiative aimed at strengthening the Black Sea country's resilience to Russia's hybrid war. However, the performance of the department was critically assessed by the Georgian experts considering the fact that in contrast to the East Stratcom, the Georgian part did not publicly communicate the outcomes of media analysis and disinformation rhetoric. Moreover, none of the official state strategies and respective action plans adopted by the Georgian government address the threats related to hybrid warfare or Russian disinformation, nor do they outline any strategies to combat these issues. In addition, the NATO-supported Georgian StratComs division has been accused of using trolls to attack opponents and disseminate anti-Western disinformation. Thus, it is vital for the Georgian government to undertake efforts to rebuild and improve the reputation of the local StratComs division and guarantee its functioning within its mandate.

The Ministry of Education, Science, Culture and Sport of Georgia has the capacity to support the development and integration of comprehensive media literacy programs in

schools, aimed at teaching critical thinking, fact-checking, and the identification of disinformation.

Media outlets, particularly the Georgian Public Broadcaster, can play a crucial role in planning and launching extensive public awareness campaigns about disinformation tactics and promoting responsible media consumption.

Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation (SRNSF) can significantly contribute to enhancing the operational capacity of fact-checking organizations by launching grant programs through which independent fact-checking and media organizations can verify information spread in various media channels and work on debunking false narratives in close partnership with EUvsDiSiNFO, the European Union flagship project, led by East Stratcom. Within the scope of the SRNSF mandate, funds can be allocated to grant independent research and media organizations to conduct regular assessments of public awareness regarding disinformation and the effectiveness of anti-disinformation measures.

4. Spain

4.1. Abstract

Despite the conventional left-right divide, which at times could underpin different standpoints regarding the EU and high levels of political parallelism across the media sphere, Spain displays a strong pro-European consensus. Even when certain EU policies are questioned, the criticism amounts to soft-Euroscepticism, the goal of which is to strengthen EU integration as a whole. However, the identification with the European project is more obvious among Spanish elites than the Spanish public. As a partner of the EU-funded MEDIATIZED EU project, Nebrija University has conducted media analysis, interviews with representatives of media and political elites, as well as a general population survey. Together, they shed light on the role of media and elite discourses in framing public perception of the EU and the European integration project. The research conducted also suggests that Spain has attempted to assert a leadership role in the EU, at times by adopting a sound stance toward dominant EU counterparties in key issues, such as the energy crisis, but also by opposing the ultra-right-wing governments from Eastern Europe, which has served to bolster its position of a genuine representative of European values in the EU. While pragmatic considerations remain dominant in evaluating Europeanization in Spain, identitarian considerations should not be fully discarded.

4.2. Executive Summary

For the purpose of media analysis, we selected six representative outlets based on their ownership (public/private), format (traditional/digital), editorial line (conservative/liberal), and type of media (TV/newspapers). The outlets include ABC, Antena 3, El Confidencial, edDiario.es, El País, and RTVE; their Twitter accounts were used, as well. Accordingly, almost all of the discourses reflect a clear pro-European sentiment. Even the discourses that are critical of the EU, they display soft Euroscepticism; the case in point is the discourse maintaining that the EU needs to consolidate its geopolitical weight in order to protect its members, or the discourse maintaining that the EU needs to adopt a more robust policy regarding the management of migration crises capable of impacting European security and identity. Looking at the position of 50 representatives of media and political elites in Spain (in the case of media, selected based on ownership and editorial line, and, in the case of politics, selected based on party affiliation while maintaining an accurate balance between the ideological tendencies of parties as per the number of seats they hold in the Spanish Parliament), pragmatic considerations remain dominant. The prominence of pragmatism to Europeanization is reflected in the high importance attached to issues such as the NextGenerationEU funds, geopolitics, defence, Brexit, etc. Many interviewees believe that the war in Ukraine has been a transformative experience

prompting increased collaboration among member states in the field of security. However, the status of Spain in the EU has triggered polarized responses, which reflects internal polarization between the left and the right, with leftist respondents praising the role of the Spanish Prime Minister, whereas the right-wing respondents being inclined to undermine his leadership. The interviewees also demonstrate that the EU can be used as a leverage to discredit political opponents by accusing them of deviating from the European values; this was evident, for example, in the statements relating to the protection of rule of law. Finally, the public opinion survey of 1,000 people shows that 60% of them favor European integration and believe that it should go further, 19% believe that it has already gone too far, and 21% are neutral. People from the “left” are more supportive of European integration than people from the “center” and from the “right.” In addition, individuals with a higher level of trust in institutions and those who gather information from different media outlets are the most supportive of integration. Still, looking at the level of trust in media, distrust (46%) is more prevalent than trust (26%). Both people who often talk about politics and those who are uninformed are more distrustful of the media. In terms of polarization, the majority of respondents (7 out of 10) consider that the Spanish media are “polarized” and “distort reality.” Informed and highly informed respondents believe to a larger extent that the media in Spain are polarized.

4.3. Policy Recommendations

1. **Provide more coverage of EU topics and EU policies. The strong pro-EU sentiment does not guarantee a high level of knowledge of EU affairs.** When asked about basic EU information, the vast majority of respondents (90%) answered correctly that the Government of Spain voted in favor of the sanctions against Russia. Six out of ten respondents in Spain answered correctly that Croatia and Malta are effectively members of the EU, while just over half of them (52%) know that Norway, on the contrary, is not part of the EU. Overall, 14% of respondents gave a correct answer to all four questions, while 26% were only able to give one or no correct answer. As per our research, both Spaniards and political parties display a lack of interest in European affairs. However, more recently, the war in Ukraine has opened a fresh set of questions regarding the future of Europe, including the EU’s prospects to withstand competitors such as China and Russia. In response to the crisis, Spanish media outlets have shown more interest in EU affairs, and thus provided more space for issues concerning EU norms and values, as well as those in relation to defense and security policies. The lack of knowledge about EU policies also involves that the political debate does not differentiate between the adoption of policies – the realm of the EU – and the execution of those policies by national authorities. Such a lack blurs the line between the responsibilities of EU institutions and those of national governments. The confluence of Spanish political polarization and a lack of

understanding of EU mechanisms often distorts Spanish society's perception of EU policy actions.

2. **Encourage in-depth EU-related debates that would simultaneously accommodate representatives of both the left and the right.** While the EU has never been a contested political project in Spain, it has been used to fuel internal polarization between the left and the right, with each camp occasionally accusing the other party of deviation from European values. Put differently, according to Spanish media elites, discourses on European politics are heavily instrumentalized by national political parties. Despite a shared pro-European attitude among these parties, resulting in non-polarized coverage of the EU, there is no bipartisan position on European affairs. Indeed, it can be argued that there is no constructive debate about Spain's position within the EU, as both the government and the opposition exploit the European debate as a means to delegitimize the political adversary. In this regard, Spanish media elites convey that the political and media noise within Spanish politics often distorts EU messages and policies. The existing polarization of Spanish politics, which permeates the entire political debate, may explain the politization of the European discourse by political parties. For example, migration is one of those topics where disagreements are present. Moderate parties from both the left and the right tend to call for more support and involvement on the part of the EU in the management of migration, especially in member states facing massive influxes of irregular immigrants. However, the radical left is more critical of the idea of "Fortress Europe," and it accuses EU institutions of hypocrisy and a racist bias in the treatment of migrants, whereas the conservative parties rather demand the EU to be more restrictive in the admission of migrants. Likewise, parties tend to agree on the necessity of strengthening the strategic autonomy of the EU, but left-wing parties see dependence on NATO as excessive while right wing-parties understand that both organizations must cooperate and reinforce each other. As to blocking Poland and Hungary from European funds due to concerns regarding human rights and the rule of law, while major parties generally agree that both countries have deviated from European values and therefore should suffer consequences, right-wing politician, especially from the extreme right, were more likely to question whether Poland and Hungary deserve to be sanctioned.
3. **Confront Euroscepticism by talking about Spain's benefits from EU membership.** In asking the Spanish population whether or not they believe Spain has benefited from its EU membership, we see that the vast majority believe that it has been beneficial to the country (86%). This idea is greater in left-wing people, in respondents with a higher level of trust in institutions, and in "highly informed" people. Also, the higher the level of education suggests the greater the perception of benefits of EU membership, both in terms of the country itself and benefits for citizens proper. With regard to the personal benefit that it has entailed for citizens, we also see a high consideration, as 3 out

of 4 respondents believe that being in the EU benefits them. Looking at the negative aspects related to Spain, we see that about 4 out of 10 respondents believe that EU aid comes with imposed conditions that harm Spain. Even though the discourses critical of the EU tend to display soft Euroscepticism, they should not be ignored, especially given the amount of major EU challenges. As per the analyzed discourses, the EU is expected to consolidate its geopolitical weight in order to protect the security of its members, to harmonize its policies in order to be able to manage migration crises, and so on. To control Euroscepticism, it is important that the public understand benefits granted by EU membership; in fact, the 2023 Spanish EU Council Presidency felt strongly about European unity; this, when complemented with Spanish progress in terms of economic performance, further explains Spain's reputation as a pro-European country. For example, more emphasis should be placed on the NextGenerationEU funds, which mark a turning point in the European project and represent a big deal for both Spain and Europe. Most recently, Spain has approached the war in Ukraine as a transformative moment for the EU, strongly supporting the defence of some of the EU's core values, mainly freedom and democracy. However, even though Spanish media elites highlight the importance of the narrative grounded in the idea that the EU serves as the last safety net for Spanish society, such a narrative is also used by both the government and the opposition, as well as the media outlets aligned to their ideological tendencies, to construct their political narratives against each other. Conservatives criticize certain government decisions by framing them as contrary to core EU principles such as the rule of law and the separation of powers. Left wing journalists, on the other hand, position EU principles as a barrier against nationalist identitarian tendencies of the right-wing or those seeking to undermine the democratic process. Consequently, the EU becomes a legitimizing device wielded by political parties against their adversaries, which might prompt confusion among the public and more Euroscepticism in the long run.

4. **Consult the public more.** Based on the population survey, eight out of ten respondents believe that they have no influence on important decisions in Spain. This perception appears to be especially concerning among the most educated population (84.1% with university degree, and 84.5% among the youngest (18 to 29 years), 85.4 % among middle-aged respondents (30 to 44 years) held this view). The perception about the influence of people on the matters of importance in the country is greater in women than in men. People with a left ideology generally attach a higher level of influence to individual impact compared to center or right respondents. The distrust in institutions is greater among men than among women regarding all institutions assessed, while people with a left ideology have greater trust in institutions than center or right respondents. The sense of lack of power is indicative of an inertia that is difficult to counter, particularly in light of the lack of trust in the political system

– seven out of ten respondents distrust Spanish politicians (the middle-aged sample exhibits the highest level of distrust (73.4%), followed by the youngest group (68.5%)). Moreover, those who are least informed demonstrate the highest levels of distrust (79.6%), while the most informed manifest a percentage of 64.8%, which also remains notable. The internal polarization among Spaniards is evident when measuring trust in the Spanish government. Remarkably, 71.2% of those on the right express distrust in the left-wing government, while only 26.5% of those on the left do so. Similar results are observed in relation to trust in the Spanish Parliament, with 32% of those on the left express distrust, and 50.5% on the right do the same.

5. **Accommodate debates about Spain’s desire to play a leading role in the EU.** As part of the strong pro-European stance of the Spanish political and media elites, some discourses attempt to highlight the increasing leadership role of Spain in the EU. This is reflected in the discourse stressing that the management of the energy crisis has created a gap between Spain and the EU. These discourses faded away when the Iberian exception was accepted. Although Madrid’s approach to the energy crisis is critical of the Brussels authorities, especially in early reports on the issue, overall, the energy crisis is treated from a pro-European perspective. The active role of Pedro Sanchez in forging changes in the EU’s energy policies is indicative of Spain’s stronger position within the EU, with Spain being portrayed as an active and influential member. At times, highlighting the Spanish role in the EU leads to reinforcing power asymmetries between the East and the West, with Spain positioning itself as a true representative of Europe. This was particularly evident in discourses supporting the EU’s decision to withhold funds from Poland and Hungary due to rule of law and human rights concerns.
6. **Talk about the negative impact of disinformation and come up with a robust strategy to counter disinformation.** Given the seriousness of implications of disinformation, and the increasing difficulty to control the content circulated on social media, EU member states should be aware of the risk of discord being artificially provoked at both national and EU level. This makes it imperative for the country to prioritize addressing disinformation and keeping its technological mechanisms up to the latest standards – all in accordance with the existing and yet to be developed European initiatives. Given that the media play key role in spreading disinformation, EU governments are expected to develop frameworks that would foster collaboration between media and the state and make media owners / content creators accountable, yet without impacting on media freedom. To begin with, the public should be made aware and constantly reminded of the negative impact of disinformation. In addition, more attention should be paid to monitoring and reporting, through development of robust systems involving the state, media outlets, and technology companies. Finally, the legislative framework that would penalize spreading of false information should be effective. By implementing these measures in close collaboration

with different stakeholders, Spain and other EU members could pride themselves of a more assertive approach to countering disinformation, which would also help mitigate the adverse effects of disinformation on political polarization and public trust, ultimately contributing to a healthier and more informed democratic society.

4.4. Final Remarks

Researchers are in agreement that the world media reality prompts questions about disinformation as a powerful tool to negatively impact public opinion and decision-making processes, or, put differently, partisan media promote misconceptions about reality at least in two different ways: first, partisan outlets often question the credibility of experts whose conclusions challenge their ideology, and second, on some occasions, they promote misunderstanding of evidence. Spain is a clearly pro-European country, with genuine determination to contribute to the European integration project; this sentiment is also reflected in the fact that 86% of the respondents believe that Spain has benefited from its EU membership and 75.7% agree that these benefits have been extended to citizens. The higher the level of education suggests the greater the perception of benefits of EU membership, both in terms of the country itself and benefits for citizens proper. The pro-European sentiment is recorded despite the fact that the Spanish media are characterized by a high level of political parallelism. Indeed, our media analysis confirms the high support for the EU among political and media elites, even in times of crisis; counter-discourses showing any form of Euroscepticism are truly marginal. While the interviewed elites tend to display pragmatism and strong pro-European sentiments, the rare cases of polarization are mostly due to the typical left-right divide, which can occasionally result in the EU being used as a leverage to discredit political opponents. Finally, the surveyed population, has helped us to further understand public perception of how media and elite discourses frame the process of Europeanization, as well as what people think about the EU, and how this relates to pragmatic, identity-based, and sociodemographic explanatory variables. The variety of media outlets and the presence of media freedom overall confirm the importance of keeping media away from political influence; still, it is always important to bear in mind the possible editorial preferences of media elites (in terms of ownership and provision of funding). All of this is key in the context of the increasing risk of disinformation. In the EU, efforts to tackle disinformation began in 2015 as a response to external influences targeting EU democratic systems, mainly by Russia. This is also important since crises are often accompanied with political disaffection and Euroscepticism among electorates, and therefore they are capable of questioning the European integration project. This is key when coupled with the detrimental potential of disinformation, to which EU authorities are surely expected to pay even greater attention in the years to come.

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5. Estonia

5.1. Abstract

Estonia is an enthusiastic and committed EU Member – if membership is useful from a utilitarian and pragmatic viewpoint! Mainstream political parties are pro-EU; approximately two-thirds of people support EU membership since the pre-accession referendum until today. However, this does not translate into support for further and deeper integration. Many Estonians are hesitant about EU involvement in matters linked to the identity of the state and there is not much debate about this. EU membership is regarded as beneficial for the economy and the security of the state vis-à-vis external aggression, in addition to NATO. This utilitarian approach is reflected in media and there are few fundamental differences between different groups. The same approach is found among Russian speakers and ethno-nationalists, even if the specific issues of concern are different. Disinformation about EU 'cultural imposition' exists, often originating from outside of Estonia and spread especially in an aggressive anti-EU tone by ethno-nationalists. The challenge for policymakers is to encourage Estonians to be active Europeans who are not afraid to discuss common values that unite Europeans, in order for the population to see EU as more than just a practical matter, and to keep the debate free from disinformation aiming at undermining European unity. People should be reminded that they are EU citizens as well and consequently can influence EU policies.

5.2. Executive Summary

In Estonia, EU membership is supported by a majority of the population including groups of diverse ethnic backgrounds, age and geographical location. Across most groups, pragmatic issues are of greater interest than identity issues. It may be seen as nearly self-evident that Estonia is a European country that belongs in the European family of values, but there is less agreement on what exactly these values are. There is a degree of scepticism regarding EU involvement in identity matters. Disinformation is prevalent especially in social media to emphasise this negative perception in order to create discord among European states. Nevertheless, support for EU membership remains high for economic and practical reasons. In addition, security issues are of prime concern in Estonia especially since the start of the Russian aggression toward Ukraine and EU is seen as an additional security guarantee.

In order to strengthen the European cohesion in a landscape of increasing polarisation and risks of disinformation, we recommend attention to the question of trust in institutions, including EU institutions and the cooperation between national and EU institutions. Furthermore, the trust in media is also essential. Media can play an important role in providing better and more in-depth information about the EU, rather

than as now limiting itself often to official statements. There is a potential for utilising positive aspects of digitalisation, such as a use of technology to debunk falsehoods. Digital literacy should remain a high priority. The fight against disinformation is an essential part of cybersecurity. Attitudes and identitarian issues would benefit from being a conscious part of the media and political discourse.

There are relatively few and small differences between different groups in Estonia regarding the perception of the EU, as compared to some other Member States. There are no major differences in the media consumed by the elite and the general population, with online media being prevalent in general. There are however differences between media habits of the Russian speaking minority and the majority population. Given the absence of major Eurosceptic and populist media outlets, the ethnonationalist community consumes specialised online outlets that are quite far from the general discourse, but easily accessible and attractive options for spreading various conspiracies, fake news, and fears. Measures to improve knowledge and engage communities should take all groups into consideration.

5.3. Policy Recommendations

1. **Given the increasing polarisation and risks of disinformation, the question of trust in institutions, including EU institutions and the cooperation between national and EU institutions is essential.** The lack of trust can be combatted through better knowledge and understanding about the EU as such, its relationship with member states and member state institutions. The discussion should take all different communities in Estonia into consideration, including Russian speaking as well as ethno-nationalist communities.
2. **Given the same reasons of polarisation and disinformation, there is also a need to focus on how trust in the media can be increased.**
3. **Cybersecurity policy and strategy should include tools related to media content, directly aimed at combatting disinformation.** Disinformation is prevalent especially in social media to emphasise this negative perception in order to create discord among European states. The more disinformation spreads, the less trust do people have in media of any kind. Estonia is a very digital society, which means potential for utilising positive aspects of digitalisation, such as a use of technology to debunk falsehoods. Such efforts need practical support. Digital literacy should remain a high priority.
4. **The attitudes regarding the EU and the fears related to identitarian issues should be part of the debate.** What is largely lacking in both political debate and the media is a more value-based discussion on European issues and a proactive Estonian approach to shaping common European values. To some extent,

a growing polarisation of society has encouraged more of this debate, but it can be observed that mainstream political parties may also be hesitant about a more identitarian European debate. Exceptions to this are seen on matters of direct and dramatic importance to Estonia, like a common approach against Russian aggression. Given its status as a frontline state with experience of such aggression in the past, Estonia has been prominent in pushing for common European tools. Scepticism regarding EU involvement in identitarian matters is to some extent based on a lack of deeper knowledge and understanding concerning the EU among the general population. This scepticism is politically exploited by right-wing populists that have gained popularity over recent years, for example by claiming that the EU forces countries to accept liberal views on minorities, immigration etc. The Estonian mainstream political community and media have been hesitant in the more principled discussion about European values even if society regards itself as an obvious member of the European community.

5. **Society would benefit from a better knowledge about EU related issues in addition to just the basic facts of press releases.** This should be supported by media. Most journalists, with a few exceptions, have no real competence to discuss EU issues in depth. Instead of debate there are press releases from government and agencies. Estonian media mostly reflects global or European topics of current general interest, predominately in a pragmatic manner. The Russian language media is principally pro-European but issues which get attention in the Estonian language media may be absent and the selective treatment of European issues is even more pronounced.

5.4. Final Remarks

The project has given the opportunity for a deeper understanding of the Estonian population and its views on European issues, through a combination of media analysis, interviews, and surveys. The research has shown that the elite views are more diverse than the black and white media picture, on pragmatic and identity factors. Positions of different groups including pro/anti EU interviewees may even coincide on some issues. There is a strong self-identification as 'European' among all major interest groups, including ethnonationalist and Russophone discourses. Nevertheless, Eurosceptic ideas can easily get support in segments of the society. Scepticism tends to arise on sovereignty and identity issues or EU involvement in what is seen as national issues. Identitarian discourses are primarily used by Eurosceptic outlets. Estonian media mostly reflects global or European topics of current general interest, predominately in a pragmatic manner. Security issues, not least related to the war in Ukraine, and the immigration crisis in Belarus are examples of issues that get attention. A majority of Estonians are in favour of common European security positions and also agree that environmental and trade issues shall be handled at a European level. Nevertheless, the support for European values is often presented by media and the political debate as a

polarising issue, where the EU if not enforces its values, at least expects member states to adjust.

6. Portugal

6.1. Abstract

Portugal's public debate showcases a positive attitude towards its integration into the EU and towards the Union itself. Criticisms mobilising structural and conjunctural aspects are voiced mainly by the left, but also by the right, though with little media space and remaining backstage. Different views on the EU coexist, but the debate does not follow a pro- or anti-EU divide logic, resting rather on distinct views of advantages and disadvantages, benefits and costs. This makes Portugal an interesting case, with no major forces mobilised as hard Eurosceptics – at least for the moment. The study characterises and analyses the main conditions and concerns behind the different attitudes towards the Europeanisation process. Considering the growing polarisation in Europe and the rising influence of extreme-right parties, but also the pertinence of criticisms and concerns identified in the study in socioeconomic, security, information, citizen engagement, and other matters, this analysis unpacks the mediatised discourse on Europeanisation in Portugal as well as elite and public perceptions of these processes to better grasp how these are framed in-context and regarding positionality. Based on these analyses, this document identifies priorities for policymaking and outlines recommendations in the main areas of concern emerging from the study.

6.2. Executive Summary

The Portuguese political and media elites and public opinion are generally aligned in favour of EU integration and have a very positive view of the Union. Criticisms exist in conjunctural or structural aspects voiced but tend to be cornered in terms of the media space and, politically, are mainly voiced by the right-wing and, especially, by the left. Despite this critical assessment of the EU, and conversely to other countries, instead of a pro- and anti-EU divide, the public debate has unfolded within a margin of discussion marked by a discourse of advantages and disadvantages of integration and of Portugal's role in this project, prioritising a rational focused on pragmatic elements, namely the economy, with social, political, environmental, technological, and security issues compounding the debate. Axiological aspects are also embedded in both dominant and counter discourses and sometimes enmesh with the former.

These discursive constructions go in line with Portuguese foreign policy towards the EU - which has consistently and coherently approached the EU as a political project to which the country naturally belongs and as a tool to continuously evolve towards progress and modernisation.

In this context, the main findings show that in Portugal the media has "normalised" news about the EU among other domestic affairs, and, although informative diets are always produced taking into account gatekeeping logic, there are no censored

discourses, with criticism taking mostly place in opinion pieces and interviews. Yet, most of the coverage is still predominantly superficial and over-reliant on official sources – namely, Portuguese and EU authorities, which translates into the reproduction of a dominant and institutional-based discourse about Portugal’s Europeanisation and integration. Both positive views and criticisms are better explored in in-depth interviews with different political actors from left- to right-wing parties and media professionals involved in news production, who provided a nuanced perspective of their opinions of the process. Among the public, there is an overwhelming support for integration and a sense that this is a very beneficial process, but different socio-demographic conditions have clearly affected how people get information about, understand, and engage with this project, confirming previous findings that there is a gap to bridge between the EU and its citizens.

6.3. Policy Recommendations

1. **Diversify the political spectrum of opinions voiced and foster specialisation to deepen debates on the EU.** Overall media trust is high in Portugal, nevertheless, quality and independent reporting/journalism requires material conditions that have been found lacking. As information vehicles covering EU issues, media should ensure greater depth and even greater diversity of perspectives on the news itself, produce more reportages, debates and investigative reports, and expand the space for larger political and ideological representation concerning experts, specialists, social organisations, political parties from the whole spectrum and citizens themselves, promoting a broader, in-depth and participated debate about the EU; foster specialisation on EU topics among journalists and media representatives allowing deeper coverage and broader debates.
2. **Create and implement assertive strategy to counter disinformation.** The use of disinformation in political disputes, with effects on political polarisation and mistrust in public institutions, should be the focus of attention in the overall country’s strategy to tackle this trend. Despite the several mechanisms and institutional framework in place, quite institutionalised and in-line with European initiatives, a more assertive strategy to counter disinformation should be in place, particularly in articulation with the media, in order to assure wider outreach and responsibility-ownership from both the political sector and these key actors in the information sphere.
3. **Allow a political and social atmosphere that is prone to in-depth, constructive and critical debates.** The media and political elites converge in that there is no polarisation in media coverage of politics, however the population survey shows otherwise: 40% agree that there is polarisation and only 14% disagree with that claim, with the remaining respondents neither

agreeing or disagreeing. The way EU issues are represented in the media and political debates should be informative, with more in-depth and comparative analysis that can both highlight common grounds as well as constructively deal with democratic, political contention. Particular attention should be paid to news titles and political leaders should clarify their positioning on EU matters, which are often mixed with domestic issues and instrumentalised in their contest for space in the media. This practice generates confusion regarding tasks-division and decision-making responsibilities between the Portuguese government and the EU level. Whereas the right-wing growth in Portugal has not led to a radicalisation in polarised discourse or an anti-EU narrative, the soft-Eurosceptic approach should be amply perceived by society not to foster imaginary divides, but to allow a political and social atmosphere that is open to critical debates; how the political space is populated is the responsibility of political parties as well as of media reporting and coverage.

4. **Overcome superficial “normalisation” of the EU.** There is not a pro-EU/anti-EU divide in Portugal, but rather a dominant centrist perspective, with critical perspectives emerging from the left- and right-wing holding little space in the media. Pragmatism has been the major rationale informing and organising arguments and attitudes towards the EU, both in supportive and optimistic senses and in critical and cautionary warnings, particularly regarding the economy/development. It is also perceptible in the overall very positive attitude of the population survey respondents towards the EU in general, and in particular sectoral areas (e.g. economic development (56%), social welfare (30%), human rights and democracy (28%), security (25%), migration (18%), and green policies (17%)). Identitarian considerations have also informed attitudes, although mostly implicitly and to a minor degree, with no signs of nationalist trends opposing the EU or what it represents in identity terms. Decision-makers should be aware of this trend of a superficial “normalisation” of the EU in political and media discourses and better clarify policy options, unpacking what these pragmatic issues mean in practical terms for Portugal and engaging with concerns raised by several actors, including the overall civil society, professional associations and unions, the productive sector, and so forth. There should also be more debate on and attention to the trend of increasing security and defence capabilities in the EU and Portugal’s positioning on fundamental issues, as human rights, democracy and security are topics of ample concern in Portuguese society. The environment, climate change and green policies are also on the agenda and political and media actors should further focus on clear information about political options and current debates.
5. **Foster civic interest and engagement with the EU through participation and informing in-depth debates.** Results show a low level of trust in Portuguese politicians and institutions, despite recognition of the influence of people like the Prime Minister or a Member of Parliament. The way the Portuguese government manages EU-related issues was a source of discontent, particularly

in economic and trade terms, which emerge as the most pressing issues amidst media and political elites and the population. The political debate about the range of issues associated with the EU should foster civic interest and engagement in a practical and direct way, which should be translated into more informed debates and contributions from civil society to normative and political initiatives. Moreover, the way politicians frame the issues on the political agenda will also affect their mediatisation and engagement from the public at large.

6. **Further knowledge and literacy on political and EU related issues.** Political engagement and knowledge on the EU are generally low amidst the Portuguese surveyed, and better results are correlated to the level of education and income —i.e., those better educated and earning more demonstrate better knowledge. This is an indication that there is a lack of access to quality information that promotes interest in political and EU-related matters and enables civic engagement through informed participation. Promote initiatives that bring civil society organisations, including local associations, unions, and the ordinary citizen closer to EU affairs in their capacity of agents, and not only a general public, such as civic training; raise awareness in educational curricula on political issues, representativity, direct democratic participation, and institutions functioning both at the national and EU levels; ensure enlarged reach and scope of EU-knowledge as EU issues are about economics and politics, but also about social aspects, the environment, and other topics of relevance, transversal to the wider public.

6.4. Final Remarks

Overall, the Portuguese perceptions of Europeanisation are positive and especially couched on pragmatic considerations for the country's development and the economy. The Portuguese media has given space to views and perspectives from all political spectres, including those in criticism of the EU, especially in op-eds and opinion articles, and in letters from the general public, but in its mediatisation of the debate, the media have emphasised a centrist approach and thus helped normalise what became a mainstream, positive appraisal of EU integration. The soft-Euroscepticism present in Portuguese society does not translate into anti-EU positioning, thus the debates about Portuguese integration into the EU take place around the costs and benefits of this process. Despite this positive assessment, it is fundamental to assure the maintenance of a context open to debate and to critical voices, and that this is translated into actual engagement with the diverse concerns raised. This effective openness needs to be cherished in a context where increasing polarisation and radicalisation are a visible trend throughout Europe, with the curtailing of fundamental liberties and principles putting democracy in jeopardy.

To this effect, the media in Portugal should be free from political interference, and space/conditions are needed for the proliferation of alternative and citizen media that are not owned by big conglomerates. Most outlets, even those owned by big groups, also need better material conditions to produce independent and quality journalism. This will assure trust levels might be maintained, and potentially increased, with the media being a central part of the functioning of democracy. Political leadership and parties from all spectres should also convey clearly their programmes and messages in different sectorial areas with regard to the EU, avoiding misperceptions and seeking to overcome mistrust. This undermines the political process overall and paves ground for the rise of extremist groups as well as to the polarisation of society. Further literacy on EU integration would also allow better interpretation of debates and political discourse among the general population, with critical thinking contributing to in-depth analysis informing the public debates. Further integration of civil society in political processes, here especially with a focus on the EU, is also fundamental for political legitimacy. Strengthening mechanisms to counter disinformation and have a wide impact in clarifying options, decisions and contents should also be a priority in a context where disinformation practices are at the service of polarisation and also fundamentally undermine democratic processes.

7. Belgium

7.1. Abstract

The Belgian political and media elites and public opinion are generally aligned in favour of EU integration but a new and far more pragmatic pro-European sentiment which is noticeable. Far-right and more security-oriented discourses are well established across the Belgian media-landscape, especially across Flemish broadcasters and news. The general perception that Belgian populist fringes are all anti-EU isn't entirely correct. Instead, the perceptions of Belgian citizens and its media environment is more complicated and compartmentalized. As was largely expected, opinions vary greatly between Wallonia and Flanders, but more important is the age of respondents as well as the topic of stake. This means that a new generation of Belgians are far more pro-EU than their previous generation, and they are particularly interested in delegating authority to the EU when it comes to energy, security, migration and the environment. Interestingly, respondents show a relatively high level of trust in the EU, as well as in media more broadly. However, this is not the same idealistic representation of the EU, as had been observed in previous years. Both popular and media perceptions about the EU are increasingly pragmatic and viewed from a security and migration prism.

7.2. Executive Summary

Overall, the Belgian political and media elites as well as public opinion showcase a generally high level of pro-EU sentiment and narrative. In addition, it is observable both from our quantitative and qualitative data that a surprisingly favorable level of trust for both EU institutions and media stakeholders like journalists exists across the Belgian population. It should however be said that the EU is perceived differently, depending on age and location. Flemish respondents generally have less knowledge about and are less supportive of the EU compared to their Walloon counterparts. In addition, the young people (age group 18-29) and older people (65+) are more attached to the European Union than those in between. These popular observations are very connected to what we observe in our media analysis over a prolonged period of time (2021-2022) in which it is clear that the Flemish media and broadcasting laws favor a more unregulated and liberalized content production, which - in turn - fosters higher levels of populist media, click-bate type sensational news and unfiltered access to far-right discourses. It is noteworthy that no "cordon sanitaire" for media exists in Flanders, whereas Wallonia doesn't allow for far-right coverage in their media sphere. Beyond these points, it is clear that both across popular opinion and the media analysis a new and more pragmatic form of pro-EU discourse is rising, often hidden amongst basic Euroskepticism. These narratives are less based on values, business, or ideas of Europe, while instead supporting a pragmatic and security-oriented form of cooperation with the main target being external threats ranging from terrorism, third-party countries

and illegal migration. Such far-right security-oriented discourses are well established across the Belgian media-landscape, especially across Flemish broadcasters while topics like “weaponization of migration” and even slightly-pro Russian narratives are also observable with regards to the war in Ukraine and pricing of energy. It is a mistake to perceive these trends as entirely anti-EU. On the contrary, they showcase a form of pro-EU stance based on more right-wing values, which instead priorities new topics. In short, people across all of Belgium believe that the EU should be in charge of more global-regional policies, which cannot be solved locally, including energy, security, migration and the environment.

7.3. Policy Recommendations

1. **Create tailor-made, topic-specific EU campaigns.** The EU is often an easy target for disgruntled citizens, who need someone to scapegoat. Its anonymous and bureaucratic nature makes it an easy target, while the EU has - for a long period - primarily catered to party-political progressive and multi-cultural audiences as well as business and elites. As half of the Belgian citizens believe that Belgium has benefited from its EU membership, it is essential to explain the real EU benefits through campaigns that include multi-demographic messages, that are tailored to different needs and views in society, stratified according to education levels, geography, age (especially young and elder people), ideology and gender. In addition, it is vital to make this campaign topic-specific, where the Belgian public is ready to attribute more roles to the EU, namely energy, security, migration, and environment, while it is also recommendable to explain the EU’s budgetary role in structural economic support through cohesion, structural and agricultural funds. Increasing knowledge of the EU is important for all Belgian citizens, particularly for Flemish speakers, who generally show less understanding and support for the EU compared to their Francophone counterparts.
2. **Foster media diversity by supporting innovative new online media initiatives and channels.** In Belgium, only a handful of small-scale online local outlets are available, and most of them struggle to gain traction despite the fact that online news platforms are the second most preferred news source after TV. Additionally, 42% of Belgian citizens believe that media coverage in the country is polarized. Therefore, there is a need to diversify the media landscape while also supporting innovative new online media initiatives and channels. Additionally, since the above-mentioned dissemination and outreach are exercises that go beyond simple adverts and paid commercials, they necessitate cooperation and funding support for influencers, content producers, artists, celebrities, media stakeholders, think tanks, non-governmental organizations, academics, public intellectuals, and local citizen organizations. Without new,

innovative media initiatives producing high-quality content, campaigns will struggle to reach targeted groups and achieve the desired success.

3. **Countering disinformation and increasing media literacy.** Despite recent improvements in countering disinformation across the EU, it is noteworthy that continued forms of media-literacy-digital-information (in 'short form' on reels) need to be developed and actively shared by governments. In addition, there is a real need for active outreach to online influencers, media personalities, and journalists to produce stories that de-bunk disinformation and/or actively produce content. In short, it is not enough to have one website or profile (e.g. EU vs. Disinformation) that debunks myths, since most European citizens do not visit this single website. Instead, it is important to have a network of active media stakeholders and online content producers that, with support from EU versus Disinformation and other sources, actively produce high-viewership entertainment content and/or journalism that advocates true and verified stories tailored to Belgium. Another important factor is also linking online influencers and content producers in Belgium with their counterparts in Ukraine, Türkiye, Central Asia, Western Balkans, Caucasus, and North Africa, so as to allow them to exchange views, ideas and information with reliable counterparts abroad. Lastly, in order to foster a more balanced view of the EU diverse media representations that reflect both Francophone and Flemish.

4. **Collaborate with the EU to develop more EU-level media legislation in tandem with the Digital Service Act (DSA) and establish media councils within Belgium.** The use of disinformation has a severe impact on political polarisation and mistrust in public institutions, necessitating a more assertive strategy to counter disinformation. This includes aligning definitions of disinformation, implementing Artificial Intelligence training procedures, and enhancing overall accountability. Stricter regulatory frameworks for social media companies should be harmonized at EU levels, with data stored and processed inside the EU (e.g. GDPR). However, such levels of regulatory censorship by politicians and big tech companies will not be deemed acceptable, unless digital and media councils are established, which continuously provide input to regulators. These councils should include a wide range of non-governmental and local actors, including randomized samples of citizens, academics, and think-tankers from across the political party spectrum (e.g. extreme left, right, center, etc.), to ensure consensus and legitimacy in addressing the delicate balance of information-space and freedom of expression. In addition to all of this, Belgian citizens desire closer cooperation with the EU, as survey results indicate high dissatisfaction with the federal government's handling of EU-related matters. Collaborating with the EU to develop more EU-level media legislation will increase areas of cooperation between Belgian government and the EU and therefore automatically address the population's dissatisfaction.

5. **Engage with Euro-sceptic “fringe society” and conditionally EU-optimist group differently.** The Belgian government should make a concerted effort to engage with increasingly marginalized segments of society. Simultaneously, efforts should be directed towards those who are conditionally supportive of the EU. Addressing Euroscepticism involves a multifaceted approach that includes engaging with Eurosceptic groups to foster understanding and provide accurate information. Such efforts necessitate both public and non-public outreach, dialogue, exchanges, content production, and research, in which non-elite parts of media, politics, economy, and society engage more with usual actors of governance and policy, including through municipal discussions, citizens assemblies, and online discussion forums. For the second group (conditionally EU-optimists) efforts should focus on addressing their reservations while reinforcing their positive views and taking into consideration both pragmatic and identity considerations they have. This includes highlighting EU efforts to improve accountability with border management (Frontex) and uphold human rights standards, as well as engaging on issues like LGBTQ rights and democracy and developments regarding the accession process of Ukraine, Moldova, and Georgia. New topics are increasingly more popular at the EU level, while the EU’s mandate and communication tools remain outdated in comparison to the 21st century needs.

7.4. Final Remarks

It is clear that Eurosceptic sentiment across the information space, and most notably in the EU media, is linked to a variety of factors, as this study’s complex methodological data collection suggests. In the case of Belgium, the aforementioned recommendations should be diligently followed to avoid a steady rise in Euroscepticism and citizen alienation, which carries the potential of rendering the EU dysfunctional unpopular and increasingly distant from voters. In the age of disinformation and at a highly securitized time in which policy decisions across democracies should be rendered more effective, it is of particular importance that the EU supports a well-funded policy of countering disinformation more effectively, more locally, and with new audio-visual and content producing digital tools tailored made for different audiences. New and far more comprehensive, localized, tailor-made and digital toolbox of policies, ranging from regulatory frameworks and new disinformation methods to citizen engagement and outreach are urgently needed if the EU and its members aim to continue its process of integration with popular support. Finally, as a large number of governments are shifting from mainstream to fringe parties, while media channels are increasingly decentralized, it is important to reach out to fringe elements of society, including polarized citizens, associations, local government, political parties, online influencers, and non-traditional or oppositional content producers.

8. Hungary

8.1. Abstract

Two framework conditions are crucial in understanding the Europeanisation discourse in Hungary. First, both politics and the media are asymmetrically polarised, with the predominant influence of the governing elite. This asymmetric polarisation explains the characteristics of the discursive blocs, both in terms of their size and influence, and their orientation towards the EU. The dominant governing bloc shows hard sovereignist and often explicit anti-EU discourse and behaviour while the smaller non-government bloc provides more positive discourse features towards Europeanisation although their voice is constrained among the prevailing media context. The other framework condition is that the Hungarian public has not lost its support and interest in the EU – whatever discourse features are presented by the government actors and their media outlet. This contrast provides the particularity of the Hungarian case.

Given the dominance of the government's anti-EU discourse this policy brief notes concerns whether the policy recommendations that are built on the research findings of the MEDIATIZED EU project can be implemented. Nevertheless, this policy brief ambitions that decision makers irrespective of their political belonging observe these findings and consider the possible steps further. The outlined context requires that these policy considerations look beyond the most frequent agents of policymaking.

8.2. Executive Summary

The pro-government media, which make up roughly two-thirds of the observed corpus, have developed and maintain a negative and polarising discourse about the EU, while the non-government media mostly report neutral or balanced information on the EU. In all anti-Brussels discourse, the EU appears as an external and alien actor or even as a threat against national sovereignty and identity. The government's domestic politics is firmly embedded in the anti-EU discourse, and the blame game is applied not only to the EU as such but also to opposition actors that are claimed to serve outside interests.

In addition to the media analysis the research used elite interviews to reveal the fundamental opinion of the political and the media elite about the EU and particularly Hungary's relation to it. The strongest factor included pro-integration views, and its defining claim was that EU membership is beneficial for Hungary. The second strongest factor, sovereignty, emphasised that the EU's institutional developments and symbolic gestures threaten national sovereignty. The multi-speed and Huxit factors represented a small minority within the elite – the latter exclusively featuring extreme right. The hard Eurosceptic and sovereignist discourse overarches both the identity and pragmatic aspects about the of EU although the identity aspects are more explicit and the pragmatic aspects remain blurred and miss factual information.

One difference between the political and media elite is that sovereignty is the dominant discourse among politicians, while pro-integration is the dominant discourse among the media elite.

MEDIATIZED EU research also conducted a representative survey among the public. The majority of the public have positive views about the EU, namely that it has clear benefits for Hungary both in economic terms and in international politics. They also show higher level of trust in EU institutions than in the domestic ones. As for the discourse related views the relative majority of the population sees the Hungarian elite divided, and the absolute majority of the public would expect greater unity of the elite concerning EU-issues. Similarly, people tend to believe that the media is polarised and distorts reality. At the same time it became evident that people are underinformed, and they often understand the concepts such as sovereignty or multi-speed Europe differently or are even misled by anti-EU government propaganda.

8.3. Policy Recommendations

1. **The toxic polarisation of the media should be overcome. Toxic polarisation of the media is harmful in a number of respects.** Most prominently it will strengthen anti-pluralist and non-democratic forces as they enjoy the advantages of polarisation. Furthermore, it will lead to biased information provision and it will destroy public belief in fair and correct information, a condition that can either push citizen opinion towards extreme positions or increase passivity among them as extremities per se discourage large parts of the population to interact. Ever-increasing polarisation only supports the non-democratic tendencies. This process has been internationally proven and can be confirmed by the political trends in Hungary: the transformation from democracy through electoral democracy to electoral autocracy took place amongst ever growing polarisation. As polarisation is the immanent interest of the government forces the lines of polarisation should not be strengthened. We suggest two policies to overcome polarisation: refocusing policy themes and refocusing on relevant actors. By introducing policy themes, by developing and presenting new topics for the public eye would and could divert attention from the widely used polarising themes and thus transform discourse. By introducing new actors and through new alliances, let them be civic organisations or experts or any other groups and agents who could add new perspectives, polarising agenda can be successfully challenged. Overall, the media both in terms of developing and communicating new themes and actors should be a major actor to halt and reverse toxic polarisation.
2. **Measures against misinformation should be implemented.** Our research has found that a large proportion of citizens actually feel targeted by misinformation, fake news, including international propaganda originated in

third countries on important matters of international politics. For example, as regards exposure to disinformation and fake news, only one in fifteen among the public say they have never experienced it, while two in five say they have often encountered it. These are startling findings. In addition to the exposure to actual fake news misinformation will add to misleading opinion formation and will eventually reinforce political forces that question the advantages of the European project or democratic potentials of pluralist politics. For example, the assertions that Hungary is the bearer of true European values and that the Hungarian economy has performed better than the European average were questioned only by those respondents who can be placed in the federalist group, the others to smaller or larger degree confided in these factually untrue statements. The impact of misinformation is evident as those who are informed exclusively by pro-government media, show less support for further integration than the average.

3. **The knowledge level about the European Union should increase.** The knowledge level of the public about the EU should be increased so that they can comprehensively evaluate information and discourse in this regard. As the EU is further away from the voters than from their national polity it is more difficult for them to properly understand the multilevel political and policy space. For example, the categories that are used by the elite and appear in the news evaluating the EU such as sovereigntism or multi-speed Europe are often difficult to contextualise for the public. Even though HUXit is a marginal anti-EU discourse both among the elite and the public those who share this view are typical government-supporters. Being uninformed causes vulnerability. Because the conceptual tools of sovereigntism are too abstract, part of the pro-government public opinion draws radical conclusions about HUXit from the government's EU related criticism. Non-government (opposition) parties in Hungary tend to be modest in providing substantive information about EU related affairs and about their party viewpoints in this regard. The voters face this condition in a context when from the pro-government media non-factual anti-EU propaganda constitute the discourse. Thus, the non-government parties should clarify and specify their policy stances about the EU. This could ease information-hunger and help substantiate the public's broad EU sympathies that we have identified in the MEDIATIZED EU research. This approach as an information policy requirement should prevail not only close to or in relation to electoral events – although in those periods it is the most compelling. Instead, these topics should be permanently kept on the agenda.
4. **EU-related knowledge should be better reflected in education.** Information provision is a policy that fundamentally serves fair representation. From academic research we know that when voters get more information about the parties' EU related views, they are more likely to vote on the basis of their EU attitudes. In the MEDIATIZED EU research we have found that younger generations are less interested and less informed about the EU than older age

groups. In education policy fundamental policy changes would be necessary. An entire complex program of civic education incorporating EU affairs would be necessary to educate conscious citizens who can make responsible decisions. Some smaller steps could also work for a start. For example, the EP Liaison Office for Hungary could organise meetings and discussion forums in secondary schools to provide information on concrete EU related affairs.

5. **Smear campaigns should be stopped.** We formulate this policy consideration particularly with regard to EU and domestic connections although nasty media stich-ups are not rare against domestic opposition actors, still anti-EU smear campaigns might have imponderable consequences on Europeanisation in Hungary. The EU affairs are undoubtedly international and domestic affairs in all member states. Nevertheless, the discourse features of this natural connection between the EU and national politics might well raise concerns in countries where toxic discourses and enforced media polarisation prevail. The pro-government media and government forces aim to increase their domestic electoral support by blaming the EU decisionmakers for their own failed policies in the home front. At occasions when the EU is particularly targeted for example wrongfully accused of policy or political intentions, or EU leaders appear as ridiculous or threatening characters on tens of thousands of billboards all over the country it can be rightly expected that the EU authorities pursue campaigns or counter-campaigns to clarify false and even poisonous information. When this type of poisonous propaganda remains unreflected by the EU this will damage the public views on the EU and it will have detrimental consequences prospectively. These smear campaign should be stopped with clear political and policy steps that should originate at the EU level.
6. **Allow and develop balanced opportunities for diverse non-government actors.** Among the conditions of asymmetric polarisation and authoritarian politics pro-government centralised discourses prevail. A large number of relevant actors cannot make their voices heard. Opportunity inequalities acquire both a political face and a territorial face due to the extreme centralisation of governance. Local media have been usurped by the government media conglomerate. Local resources depend on the centre. Executive aggrandisement and fundamental democratic decline undermine the opportunities of non-government actors. Local governments, expert groups, civic organisations, associations of different kind have been seriously harmed by the policies (as well as by the discourses) of the populist government. These non-government organisations would have great potentials to work out alternative visions of relations with the EU and could channel public demands that are often invisible for government actors. Without concrete policy support in this direction the attachments to the EU might well impoverish.

8.4. Final Remarks

As of now it seems that the freedom of the media will be under increasing stress. We can base this expectation on the former developments, on the more recent government discourse features of increased polarisation, and the declining performance of the populist regime, which further invites polarising discourse. The government actors regard media as a strategic branch of governance that should serve their political power interests.

EU is part of international and domestic politics of the member states at the same time. Moreover, the EU constitutes an increasingly internal politics affair in all member states due to the development of the EU per se: there is much more at stake in terms of policy decisions given the EU's growing policy scope than it used to be.

This changing connection between domestic and international politics is a condition that should be noted by EU decision-makers as well. The path that Hungarian politics has followed in the past 15 or so years warns about two potential traps that have already been noted by academic literature. One is how the EU will escape from the autocracy trap. As the above policy considerations suggest in an authoritarian environment the transformation of toxic discourses is getting harder. The EU is rightly expected to reflect on this. The other potential trap is that due to EU belated action to step up against autocratic developments Eurodisappointed views could develop. Those who tended to support integration might become disappointed onlookers. Overall, the current media and discourse features are seriously damaging public thinking in numerous ways and are harmful for prosperous EU-domestic connections.